

Viscometric studies and thermal characterization of interfacial polymers having aliphatic lactone ring synthesized from succinic acid and various phenols

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Abstract : This article describes the viscometric studies and thermal behavior of various polymers having pendent aliphatic lactone ring synthesized by stirred interfacial polycondensation of various dyes and terephthaloyl chloride in 1,2-dichloroethane. All the polymers were dark colored granular powder and soluble in dimethyl sulfoxide. All polymers exhibited moderate intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ ranging from 0.475–0.51 dl/g at 32 ± 0.2 °C in DMSO. The approximate number-average molecular weight (M_n) ranges between 4.2×10^3 to 4.7×10^7 g mol⁻¹ by taking upper and lower values of α and K in Mark-Houwink-Sakurada equation. The thermal transition temperature, T_g , in the range 74.9–143.3 °C of polymers was determined from DSC thermograms. The TGA thermograms of polymers had shown good thermal stability of these polymers till 300 °C.

Keywords : Stirred interfacial polycondensation, aliphatic lactone ring, terephthaloyl chloride, intrinsic viscosity, number-average molecular weight.

Introduction

In the last few decades, a large number of dyes have been used for the synthesis of colored polymers – a new class of materials, having chromophoric system forming part in their structure. Due to lower molar mass, monomeric dyes shows some disadvantages like – toxicity¹, releasing from and migration in dyed materials^{2,3}, etc. Tethering of these dyes in polymers have solved these problems to a large extent⁴. The literature reveals that, many researchers have reported the use of dyes, especially phenolphthalein and fluorescein in polymer synthesis. Bistrzyeki and Neneki⁵ and Mayer and Mayer⁶ led the foundation of polymer forming ability of these dyes by combining phenolphthalein/fluorescein with benzoyl chloride and alkali. Bafna and Shah⁷ developed resins from phenolphthalein and formaldehyde. Lo⁸ first made epoxy resins from phenolphthalein with epichlorohydrin and alkali. Thermotropic liquid-crystalline random copolyesters⁹, thermotropic liquid-crystalline polyphosphate esters¹⁰, optically active poly (ester-imide)s¹¹, cardo polysulfonates¹², polycynurates¹³ are also reported by

using phenolphthalein. Korshak *et al.*^{14–17} reported various polyesters and polyacrylates from phenolphthalein. By using fluorescein, phenolphthalein and its derivative Howe¹⁸ and Morgan¹⁹ synthesized several polymers. Kamogawa²⁰ reported acrylyl fluorescein polymer by using fluorescein. It has been found in literature that, only a limited number of researchers^{14,18,19,21–23} have reported the use of phenolphthalein and fluorescein, in polymer synthesis particularly by Interfacial Polycondensation Technique. Previous workers²⁴ have reported the synthesis of phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dyes – synthesized from condensation of aliphatic dicarboxylic acids and various phenols. These dyes also act as indicators in place of phenolphthalein and fluorescein in the same pH-range. But no work has been found in the synthesis of colored polymers from these phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dyes by using interfacial polycondensation technique.

This article describes the thermal behaviour of synthesized dyes, polymers and viscometric study of polymers. All the polymers have been synthesized from inter-

facial polycondensation of phenolphthalein and fluorescein type of dyes with terephthaloyl chloride. The dyes were synthesized by condensation of phenol, resorcinol, pyrogallol and β -naphthol with succinic acid, which contains aliphatic lactone ring. The interfacial polycondensation technique and its modifications are highly effective procedure for the rapid preparation of many polymers on a small scale.

Results and discussion

All the four synthesized dyes were dark colored, amorphous powder and prepared by condensation reaction with the loss of water molecules, soluble in hot alcohol and NaOH. All these dyes have changed their color in acidic and alkaline medium almost in the same pH-range, like phenolphthalein and fluorescein. Since, the structures of these types of dyes were already established²⁴⁻²⁶, so here thermal analysis of dyes has been carried out.

Thermal analysis of dyes :

Action of heat :

The actions of heat on dyes were observed under normal condition (Table 1) by simply heating the sample in a crucible. These dyes do not show any melting. Generally, all the dyes started to stick to the surface of crucible after 220 °C, for at least 5-6 °C and after that started to char with fumes; whereas, the dye synthesized by using β -naphthol neither melted nor stucked to the surface of crucible but it was simply charred.

Table 1. Data on the thermal analysis of dyes

Dye code	Action of heat in presence of O ₂ Melting/sticking temp. (°C)	DSC in N ₂ atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min	
		Entrapped/absorbed H ₂ O (temp. °C)	Melting*/decomp. (temp. °C)
D-1A	235	74.57	250
D-1B	220	89.71	225.63*
D-1C	290	86.98	298.39
D-1D	305	63.58	270.60

Differential scanning calorimetry :

The thermal behaviour of dyes was again supported by DSC thermogram (Fig. 1) in N₂ atmosphere (Table 1). From the thermograms, it has been found that, either one or two endothermic peaks are present in all the thermograms. The endothermic peak within 100 °C is

Fig. 1. DSC thermogram of dyes → D-1A, D-1B, D-1C and D-1D.

due to absorbed or entrapped water molecule in the dyes. In most of the cases, after this endothermic peak – the nature of thermogram moves parallel to the baseline to a certain temperature and after that, its deviation in upward direction takes place. This indicates the onset of decomposition of dyes after that particular temperature (Table 1).

In the case of the dye D-1B, a second endothermic peak has been observed in the thermogram. This peak may be due to melting of the dye (marked by asterisk in Table 1) and reflects the crystalline nature of this dye, although no sharp melting observed during the action of heat. The deviation of thermogram from baseline takes place around 250 °C in the case of D-1A, D-1C and D-1D which indicate their decomposition. These values of thermal analysis, more or less agrees well with the re-

ported²⁴ melting/sticking/decomposition temperature (i.e. ≥ 250 °C) in all the cases.

Viscometric studies of polymers :

The solution viscosity is an important technique for the characterization of molecular interactions occurring in the polymeric solution and is a measure of hydrodynamic volume of a polymer in a given solvent. Even at low concentration of a dissolved polymer, the viscosity of a solution relative to that of the pure solvent increases appreciably. This is due to the unusual size and shape of polymer molecules and the nature of their solutions. The viscosity of a polymer solution depends on molecular weight, temperature, concentration, nature of the solvent and also on its thermodynamic affinity. Hence, the viscosity of dilute solution is generally affected by molecular weight and molecular shape of the dissolved polymer²⁷.

The inherent viscosity has been widely used for characterizing condensation polymers. For this, we have measured the flow time of solution t (of each polymer at different dilution) and that of the pure solvent (i.e. DMSO) t_0 and calculated the 'viscosity ratio' or *relative viscosity* η_r ,

$$\eta_r = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \frac{t}{t_0} \quad (1)$$

where, η = solution viscosity and η_0 = solvent viscosity.

The fractional increase in the viscosity resulting from the dissolved polymer in the solvent called as *specific viscosity*, η_{sp} was determined as :

$$\eta_{sp} = \left(\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0} \right) = \left(\frac{t - t_0}{t_0} \right) = \eta_r - 1 \quad (2)$$

By dividing the specific viscosity by concentration (C), we got the *viscosity number* or *reduced viscosity* η_{red} :

$$\eta_{red} = \frac{\eta_{sp}}{C} = \frac{\eta_r - 1}{C} \quad (3)$$

and, calculated the logarithmic viscosity number or inherent viscosity η_{inh} as,

$$\eta_{inh} = \ln \frac{\eta_r}{C} \quad (4)$$

To get rid of the influence of entanglements on viscosity, the inherent viscosity and reduced viscosity at a series of different dilutions were determined and extrapolated to zero concentration (i.e. $C = 0$). Both η_{inh} and η_{red} plotted against concentration (C), which intercept at the same point on the ordinate and gave the value of *intrinsic viscosity* $[\eta]$ of the polymer (Figs. 2 and 3). The viscometric data on flow time of dilute solutions of polymers are given in Table 2.

$$[\eta] = \lim_{C \rightarrow 0} \eta_{red} = \lim_{C \rightarrow 0} \eta_{inh} \quad (5)$$

The intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ value of all the polymers are given in (Table 2). These values also reflect the relative reactivity of different dye molecule towards acid chloride. The polymers synthesized from phenolphthalein type of dye moiety, having $(CH_2)_2$ unit in the pendent lactone ring have shown similar value of intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ (i.e. P-1A and P-1D = 0.47 dl/g). The $[\eta]$ value of all

Fig. 2. Determination of intrinsic viscosity of polymer → P-1A and P-1B; (●) = $\eta_{sp/c}$ and (■) = $\ln \eta_{r/c}$.

Fig. 3. Determination of intrinsic viscosity of polymer → P-1C and P-1D; (●) = $\eta_{sp/c}$ and (■) = $\ln \eta_{r/c}$.

the polymers synthesized by phenolphthalein type of dyes, were much less than the $[\eta]$ value of polyester obtained by polycondensation of phenolphthalein with terephthaloyl chloride (i.e. $[\eta]=1.12$ dl/g) and isophthaloyl chloride (i.e. $[\eta]=1.78$ dl/g) by Morgan^{19,28}. These lower values of intrinsic viscosity shows the low reactivity of these dyes as compared to phenolphthalein. On the other hand, the polymers synthesized from fluorescein type of dye moiety have shown intrinsic viscosity value $[\eta]$ between 0.482–0.51 dl/g. The maximum was shown by P-1C (i.e. 0.51 dl/g). These higher values of intrinsic viscosities $[\eta]$ as compared to that obtained by the polycondensation of fluorescein and isophthaloyl chloride (i.e. $[\eta] = 0.31$ dl/g) shows the high reactivity of these dyes towards acid chloride.

As the reported polyesters from phenolphthalein or

Table 2. Viscometric data on flow time of dilute solutions of polymers

Polymer code	Conc. (C) (g/dl)	η_r	η_{sp}	$\eta_{sp/C}$ (dl/g)	$\ln \eta_r$	$\ln \eta_{r/c}$ (dl/g)
P-1A	0.430	1.168	0.168	0.39	0.155	0.36
	0.287	1.123	0.123	0.43	0.116	0.40
	0.215	1.095	0.095	0.44	0.091	0.42
	0.172	1.077	0.077	0.447	0.074	0.433
	0.143	1.066	0.066	0.46	0.064	0.448
P-1B	0.477	1.249	0.249	0.522	0.222	0.465
	0.318	1.161	0.161	0.506	0.149	0.468
	0.239	1.121	0.121	0.506	0.114	0.477
	0.191	1.095	0.095	0.497	0.091	0.476
P-1C	0.461	1.222	0.222	0.48	0.201	0.436
	0.307	1.151	0.151	0.49	0.141	0.456
	0.231	1.115	0.115	0.50	0.109	0.474
	0.185	1.093	0.093	0.50	0.089	0.481
P-1D	0.457	1.221	0.221	0.484	0.200	0.438
	0.304	1.148	0.148	0.487	0.138	0.454
	0.228	1.110	0.110	0.482	0.104	0.456
	0.152	1.074	0.074	0.487	0.071	0.467
	0.131	1.063	0.063	0.481	0.061	0.466

fluorescein with terephthaloyl/isophthaloyl chloride were linear in structure, the same have been assumed for polymers in the present investigation too. Further, there are many reports about synthesis, leading to linear polyester from interfacial polycondensation of diacid chloride with diols^{12,29,30}.

The intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ is empirically related with molecular weight of a linear polymer. The measurement of intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$, which reflects the molecular weight of the dissolved polymer is widely used for determination of number-average-molecular weight (M_n) of polymers. The Mark-Houwink-Sakurada eq. (6) relates the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ of polymer with the molecular weight M ,

$$[\eta] = KM^\infty \tag{6}$$

where, K and ∞ are constants for given polymer-solvents system at a particular temperature. As for many systems ∞ lies between 0.6–0.8 and K values are between 0.5×10^{-4} to 5×10^{-4} , taking these upper and lower values of ∞ and K , different values of molecular weight³¹ was calculated for each polymer (Table 3). These values were taken as approximate number-average-molecular weight

Table 3. Data on intrinsic viscosity and approx. number-average molecular weight range of polymers

Polymer code	[η] at 32 °C (dl/g)	Approx. number-average molecular weight range (M_n)	
		[η] = KM_n^α (g mol ⁻¹)	
		$\alpha = 0.8$ $K = 5 \times 10^{-4}$	$\alpha = 0.6$ $K = 0.5 \times 10^{-4}$
P-1A	0.478	5.3×10^3	4.2×10^6
P-1B	0.482	5.4×10^3	4.3×10^6
P-1C	0.51	5.7×10^3	4.7×10^7
P-1D	0.475	4.2×10^3	4.2×10^6

(M_n) range of polymers, and were proportional to the intrinsic viscosity [η] values.

Thermal analysis of polymers :

The thermal analysis of polymers are of great importance for the study of thermal stability, degradation study and molecular architecture of polymer¹². The thermal behaviour of polymers is of considerable technological importance and helps in designing materials for high temperature applications and for the identification purposes.

Action of heat :

The melting as well as other physical changes in polymers was not clear in a capillary melting tube under normal condition. So, the visual observations on the physical changes of all the polymers were carried out by action of heat on these polymers from 50 to 450 °C in a muffle furnace. The colour changes accompanied the transition. The DSC and TGA thermograms of polymers showed that, the transition as well as the weight-losses of sample accompanied these physical changes. None of the poly-

mers were melted but did gradually changed colour accompanied by apparent change in the structure and texture of granular powder. The texture changes and noted visual decomposition along with the temperature ranges were shown in (Table 4).

From the data it is clear that, all the polymers have shown fine needle like or swollen structure formation in texture within 200 °C without any colour change. These changes were may be due to occurrence of some phase transition within the polymers. All polymers started to blacken from original colour from 200 °C onwards except, P-1C having pyrogallol moiety. In all the cases fuming started within 250 °C, except P-1C (\approx 300 °C) and ceased gradually within 400 °C. The fuming of polymers may be related to decomposition of polymers. The polymer having pyrogallol moiety does not shown any colour change even after fuming was ceased. The colour stability in P-1C may be due to symmetrically attached -OH group at two different benzene rings.

Differential scanning calorimetry :

The DSC of polymers were carried out in N₂ atmosphere to know the glass transition temperature, T_g . At the glass transition temperature – the chain ends and a substantial number of chain segments acquire sufficient energy to overcome intermolecular restrains and undergoes rotational and translational motion. So, any structural features or an externally imposed condition, which influence the chain mobility, affects the value of T_g . The T_g of polymers depends on many factors like, chemical structure-chain flexibility, stiffness, steric hindrance, polarity, tacticity, molecular weight etc. The values of T_g

Table 4. Data for action of heat on polymers in air

Polymer code	50–200 °C	200–250 °C	250–300 °C	More than 300 °C
P-1A	No colour change, slight change in texture \approx 170	Started to blacken \approx 220, fuming started \approx 230	Fully black \approx 250, maximum fuming \approx 280	Fuming ceased \approx 360
P-1B	No colour change, increase in volume observed \approx 140–190	Started to blacken \approx 205	Fully black \approx 280, fuming started \approx 260, maximum fuming \approx 275	Fuming ceased \approx 350
P-1C	No colour change, some fine structure observed \approx 180–190	No colour change	Fuming started \approx 300 °C	No colour change, maximum fuming \approx 320, fuming ceased \approx 345
P-1D	No colour change, became shiny and swelling started \approx 180	Started to blacken \approx 210, fuming started \approx 230	Fully black \approx 260, maximum fuming \approx 285	Fuming ceased \approx 400

and other transitions shown by all the polymers are given in (Table 5) and the related DSC thermogram in (Fig. 4). The T_g values of all the polymers were in the range 74.9–143.3 °C. The polymer P-1A does not show any T_g . The above lower value of T_g as compared to, polyesters¹⁹ form phenolphthalein ($T_g = 318$ °C) and fluorescein ($T_g = 276$ °C) with isophthaloyl chloride is due to the presence of aliphatic carbon chain in the pendent lactone ring of polymers²⁶. This causes low hindrance and provides easy internal rotation about primary valence bonds, and helps in the enhancement of chain flexibility³² and lowering of T_g .

Table 5. DSC data on thermal transitions of polymers at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in N₂ atmosphere (500 °C)

Polymer code	T_g (°C)	Nature of transition	Transition due to phase transformation (°C)	Transition due to decomposition (°C)
P-1A	-	Endothermic	187.7	343.3
P-1B	74.9	do	187.6	354.1
P-1C	143.3	do	203.7	378.3
P-1D	133.9	do	198.5	359.5

The T_g values of all the polymers are in the order (P-1C > P-1D > P-1B). As all these polymers have bulky three-dimensional dye moiety, which is believed to stiffen the polymeric chain segment. This creates more hindrance in the internal rotations of C–C bond within the backbone of polymeric chain and raises temperature required for segmental motion³³. The highest T_g value among these polymers were shown by P-1C. Although, the polymers having either resorcinol or pyrogallol moiety have the closed ring structure, but those with pyrogallol moiety have shown high T_g value due to symmetrically attached -OH group at two different benzene ring^{25,26}. The polymers with β -naphthol moiety have shown next high T_g value – this is due to presence of condensed ring pattern of stiff binaphthyl unit in the polymer backbone which provides much rigidity^{25,34}.

By visual observation, during action of heat on these polymers under normal condition melting was not observed, but the polymers have shown fine needle like or swollen structure formation in texture within 200 °C. This supports that some phase-transformation may be occurs within the polymeric structure corresponding to

Fig. 4. DSC thermogram of polymers → P-1A, P-1B, P-1C and P-1D.

the endothermic peak in the temperature range 187.6 to 203.7 °C. In literature also, the mesomorphic behaviour of phenolphthalein based polyesters¹⁴ and copolyesters^{9,10} are reported. The transition peak in the temperature range 343.3 to 378.3 °C may be due to decomposition of polymer, which is also supported by action of heat on these polymers. As the nature of peak in all the thermogram is endothermic, it reflects the amorphous behaviour of polymers.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The thermal stability of polymers was studied by thermogravimetric analysis. The nature of TG curve is governed by the nature of degradation reaction, activa-

tion energy and order of reaction etc., which throws light on molecular architecture of polymer. The data on TGA of polymers are given in (Table 6) and the related thermograms are shown in (Fig. 5).

All the polymers have shown good thermal stability in nitrogen atmosphere. From the thermogram, it was evident that a small weight loss in the range 1.29–1.56% takes place within 60–70 °C, which may be attributed due to loss of absorbed moisture or entrapped solvent³⁶. The onset of thermal decomposition was taken as initial decomposition temperature (IDT) and was fixed as criteria for thermal stability in polymers. All the polymers

Fig. 5. TGA thermogram of polymers → P-1A, P-1B, P-1C and P-1D.

have shown (IDT) in the range 300–319 °C. All the polymers have shown good thermal stability up to 300 °C, and started to degrade thereafter in N₂ atmosphere till 500 °C. On the other hand, polymers with phenolphthalein type of dye moiety have shown good thermal stability as compared to those with fluorescein type of dye moiety. The polyester^{19,28} from phenolphthalein with isophthalol chloride or terephthaloyl chloride were shown

decomposition above 355 °C and 400 °C respectively while, that from fluorescein with isophthaloyl chloride around 335 °C. The lower thermal stability of polymers under present investigation as compared to the polyesters from phenolphthalein or fluorescein is due to the presence of aliphatic carbon atom in pendent lactone ring. Generally the fully aromatic polyesters shows high thermal stability as compared to polyesters having an aliphatic carbon atom in their backbone^{30,35,36}. As there was no weight loss occurred from 70 to 210 °C in TG curve, so it again supports that the endothermic peak in DSC-thermogram within 210 °C were related to T_g and phase transition temperature of polymers.

The first stage of decomposition range and the temperature at which decomposition with maximum rate (T_{max}) occurred are given for each polymer along with their percentage weight loss in (Table 6). During first stage of decomposition the weight loss was around 38.4–58.6% of their original weight. This complex nature of TG thermogram might be due to simultaneous decomposition of ester as well as lactone ring. The carbonyl linkages in the main chain and lactone ring are acting as the most vulnerable part of the polymer^{12,37} that degrades selectively³⁸ (evolved gases like CO, CO₂ and phenolic monomers) and free radicals may produce. These free radicals may further recombine to form new chemical products (predominantly H₂ and CH₄) which degrade at elevated temperature to form simple low molecular weight substances. Except, P-1A all the polymers have shown 51–67% weight loss till 500 °C. The TG thermogram of polymers again supports the DSC-peak around 343.3 to 378.3 °C and shows their relation to decomposition, because their value lies within first stage decomposition range of polymers. So, the action of heat on polymers, DSC and TGA all reflects the thermal behaviour of polymers.

Table 6. Data on TGA of polymers at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in N₂ atmosphere (500 °C)

Polymer code	IDT (°C)	Decomp. range (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	Percentage (%) weight loss				
				T_{max} (°C)	At end of decomp. range (°C)	Due to volatile matter	Till 500 °C	(%) Residue left at 500 °C
P-1A	316	316–373	360	56.20	58.6	1.29	75.7	24.1
P-1B	300	300–362	344	35.31	38.4	1.3	52.7	47.3
P-1C	310	310–358	345	52.73	53.97	1.45	66.4	33.3
P-1D	319	319–437	405	37.33	42.77	1.56	51.6	48.4

Experimental

Terephthaloyl chloride (ACROS), succinic acid and NaOH (NICE), phenol, 1,2-dichloroethane, hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid (s.d. fine chem. Ltd.), pyrogallol, *n*-heptane (CDH), resorcinol (Merck), beta-naphthol (Ranbaxy), dimethyl sulfoxide (RANKEM) used were of A.R. grade.

The flow time of polymers were measured through an Ostwald Viscometer at 32 ± 0.2 °C in dimethyl sulfoxide (i.e. DMSO). The measurement of intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ was also used to calculate the approximate number-average-molecular weight (M_n) range of polymers. For this, a German made BS-188 No. B Ostwald Viscometer was used. DSC of dyes was carried out on Mettler Toledo Model - DSC 821 (-60 to 500 °C) at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under nitrogen atmosphere. DSC of polymers were carried out on Seiko instrument (Japan) - Insta 220C (-100 to 600 °C) at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. TGA of polymers were carried out on Mettler Toledo, Model - TGA/SDTA/851 (25 to 550 °C) at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The DSC and TGA both carried out in nitrogen atmosphere.

The methodology for synthesis of dyes and polymers and their characterization by solubility test, elemental analysis, FTIR and DSC of polymers are already reported^{25,26}. But here a short description for synthesis of dyes and polymers are given.

Synthesis of dyes :

The aromatic hydroxyl compounds like - phenol, resorcinol, pyrogallol and β -naphthol (2 mole) and succinic acid (1 mole) were taken in a 500 ml round-bottom flask fitted with air-condenser, and condensed in presence of 5-6 drops conc. H_2SO_4 at 150-170 °C in an oil bath for about 6-10 h, depending upon the nature of phenol used. On completion of reaction, a solidified mass was obtained on cooling, which was purified by dissolving it in dilute NaOH and reprecipitated by dilute HCl, filtered, washed with distilled water followed by cold ethanol and dried.

Synthesis of polymers :

The required quantity of respective dyes (0.01 mole) and sodium hydroxide (0.025 mole) were dissolved in

250 ml of distilled water. The filtered dye solution was then kept in the jar of Warring Blender covered with heavy duty aluminium foil pierced at the center to place a powder funnel to introduce reagents, and stirred with high speed. A solution of terephthaloyl chloride (0.01 mole) was prepared in 40-60 ml of distilled 1,2-dichloroethane and poured into the filtered dye solution as quickly as possible. The mixture was stirred for 10-90 min at $25-32 \pm 2$ °C. The faded color of dye and increase in viscosity of the solution was the indicative of the progress of the reaction. 50 ml of distilled *n*-heptane was then added to remove some of the 1,2-dichloroethane and stirred slowly for 7-8 min, filtered, washed with distilled water and dried.

Viscometric studies :

For this (0.5%) stock solutions of all the polymers were prepared by dissolving 0.2531 g of each polymer in 30 ml dust free DMSO and left overnight for complete dissolution of polymer. The polymeric solution was then filtered using Whatman filter paper no. 42 and the filter paper was then dried in an electric oven at 70 °C for 5-6 h and weighed. The polymeric solution was then transferred to the 50 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with DMSO and shaken well. Finally, the actual concentration of each filtered polymeric stock solution was determined. Further five different dilute solutions with dust free DMSO was prepared from each polymeric stock solution, and their concentration determined. All the successive dilution of stock solution was carried out during the determination of flow time of solution by viscometer. The flow time of solvent, stock solution and successive dilution of stock solution of each polymer was measured through an Ostwald Viscometer at 32 ± 0.2 °C in DMSO. Each time 10 ml of solution was taken in viscometer. The time of efflux for the solvent was taken as t_0 and that for stock solution and five dilutions as t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4 and t_5 , respectively. Since the solutions were very dilute, density of all solutions was assumed to be equal to that of the solvent (i.e. DMSO).

Thermal analysis :

Under thermal analysis, action of heat on dyes and polymers, DSC of dyes and polymers and TGA of poly-

mers have been carried out. The action of heat was carried out in a Muffle furnace, in presence of oxygen, just to observe the physical change in color, texture and appearance. For this 5–6 mg of respective dye and polymer sample was taken in a crucible in powdered form and then kept in a Muffle furnace. The change in sample was observed on regular intervals. For DSC of dyes, 4–5 mg of dye sample was taken, to know the sticking/melting/decomposition temperature of dye. For DSC of polymers, 2–6 mg of polymer sample was taken. This analysis was carried out to know the thermal transition temperature of polymers. The TGA of polymers were carried out to know the thermal stability of polymers with percent weight loss. The weight loss vs temperature plots were used for calculating the result.

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